

SCHOOL EDUCATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020

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Abstract: -

Although there has been an increase in the number of students studying in the country, there is no denying that there is some question mark over the quality of education. There are 40,000 colleges and more than 800 universities in the country. However, the proportion of higher education in student enrollment as compared to primary and secondary education is 26.3 per cent in 2018 and now the new education policy aims to increase it to at least 50 per cent by 2035. As many points of the 1986 Education Policy have not been completed in the last 34 years, it has been pointed out that there is room for improvement in some of the issues that are incomplete by reviewing them.

Each country is working to formulate its own education policy based on its own social, political and cultural criteria to make education more effective at different levels of education. When we accept that there will be educational change, a clear strategy in education as a whole is to consider what the future might hold. In the end, it is equally true that the future of education determines the future of the country. Recently, the Government of India has said that there will be major changes in the Indian education system, meaning that the recommendations will be implemented in practice, taking into account the recommendations of experts when announcing a new education policy. Considering this changing educational policy, this paper will try to shed light on how the various policies announced in the education system will have an impact in the future. Although a small part of the overall educational transformation is small, this research

paper will try to come up with new educational policies, various innovations, with expected results. This dissertation considers some features of the National Education Policy. At the same time, these educational policies shed light on the changes that are taking place in school education. The adoption of the new policy is expected to reflect research considerations on issues that need to be addressed and how they can be addressed when changing overall school functions and practices. Based on the recommendations of an expert committee chaired by Kasturirangan, former president of the Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO), Dr. Some ideas are suggested on how these educational changes will affect the quality of education and the implementation of their objectives. The socio-economic framework of the country is expected to improve, but while improving, education will play an important role in maintaining the balance in the overall educational environment. Against this backdrop of educational change, everyone needs to embrace educational change, but what can be the consequences as a prediction of the future? This will have to be seen in the implementation of education policy for some time.

Key words – *Socio,Economic, Education framework, accountability, RTE, NEP.*

Introduction -

The real power of any country is created through knowledge. The goal of the policy is to make India a knowledge superpower by equipping college students with self-reliant skills and a high level of knowledge. We see a huge shortage of manpower in various fields in India like science and technology, education and industry but we need to focus on overcoming this shortage. The draft educational policy is based on the fundamental pillars of access, equality, quality and affordability and accountability.

The National Education Policy Drafting Committee (Chairman, Dr. K. Kasturirangan) submitted its report on 31 May 2019. The committee was set up by the Ministry of Manpower Development in June 2017. The report proposes an education policy, which will address the challenges facing the current education system in terms of access, equality, quality, affordability, and accountability. The draft policy proposes reforms and changes at all levels of education, from school to higher education. These include focusing on early childhood care, suggesting changes and appropriate improvements to the current examination system, strengthening teacher education and training, and restructuring the education regulatory framework. This includes setting up a National Education Commission to increase public investment in education, promote

and disseminate knowledge through the use of technology, and focus on vocational and adult education. It is clear from this policy that changes at various levels in the education sector are about to begin.

Objective :

1. To study various provisions of the new National Education Policy.
2. To study the features of the new national education policy.
3. To study the new national education policy and the major features of school education

Research Methods

This research article is a descriptive form of information in reference literature based on the author's observations and studies.

Features of NEP 2019

1. The new national education policy includes school education, college higher education and various vocational education including agricultural education, legal education, medical education and technical education.
2. The new National Education Policy focuses on the need and importance of vocational education, including teacher education and research and innovation.
3. An attempt has been made to integrate child care and education in the Ministry of Education, through which it will be easier to implement these educational matters (Ministry of Human Resources and Development - MHRD has been renamed).
4. This strategy also tries to focus on some of the basic skills that children should have in the proposed new structure of 5 + 3 + 3 + 4.
5. The first stage of five years (for children in the age group of 3-8 years) i.e. the basic stage looks at learning and learning through play. Basic Literacy and Numerical Skills is a mission mode approach that includes national teacher programs, therapeutic instruction assistance programs, and more. This can be seen as a remarkably important factor in the policy, which considers nutrition to be extremely important in strengthening the level of 3-8 year olds.
6. The next stage is the preparatory stage for children aged 8 to 11 years (grades 3 to 5) followed by the middle stage for students aged 11-14 (grades 6 to 8) and the secondary stage for students aged 14-18 (grades 9-12).
7. In the new national policy for school education, changes at the government level are also suggested. It has been suggested to set up a new branch of management, the State

Regulatory Authority, to regulate education in the country. The recognition of various schools will be decided by this institution. The government will also be responsible for funding and operating education in the country.

School Education and Some Important Symptoms (ref.NEP 2019) -

1. Initial Period i.e. Childhood Care and Education -

In addition to the problems of school admission, the committee has taken into account the following shortcomings in the existing childhood education programs by noting many shortcomings related to quality. (i) School curriculum that does not meet the developmental needs of the children, (ii) Lack of qualified and properly educated teachers and (iii) Inferior pedagogy colleges, schools. Currently, most of the childhood education is imparted in Anganwadas and private pre-schools. However, as we see a situation where there is less focus on the educational aspects of childhood, the draft policy recommends developing a two-part curriculum for childhood care and education. This will include the following to make the appropriate changes: (i) Guidelines for children up to three years (parents and teachers) and (ii) Educational frameworks for children three to eight years. This will be implemented by improving and expanding the Anganwadi system and merging Anganwadis with primary schools.

2. Right to Education Act, 2009 (RTE Act) - Currently, RTE (Right to Education Act) provides free and compulsory education to all children in the age group of 6 to 14 years. The draft policy recommends extending the scope of the RTE Act to include early childhood education and secondary school education, so that further expansion of education in this age group can help everyone in this right to education. This will extend the law to all children in the age group of three to 18 years.

3. In addition, the draft policy recommends and suggests that the RTE Act requires a review of recent amendments to the continuous and comprehensive evaluation and no-detention policy. It states that children should not be kept in custody only up to class VIII. Instead, schools should ensure that children reach an age-appropriate level of education and that goals are achieved.

4. Curriculum Framework- The current structure of school education needs to be restructured based on the developmental needs of the students. It will consist of 5-3-3-4 design / design: (i) five years basic phase (three years pre-primary school and classes one and two), (ii) three years preparation phase (classes three to five), (iii) three years

intermediate stage (class six to eight), and (iv) four years secondary stage (class nine to 12).

5. The Sadal Committee has mentioned and clarified that the present education system and system is focusing only on the study of facts and processes. It therefore recommends that the curriculum in each subject be reduced to its essential core content. This will create space for inclusive, discussion and analysis-based learning that will be appropriate for future purposes and planning.

6. School Examination Reforms: The Committee has noted that the current Board Examinations: (i) force the student group to focus only on certain subjects and some efforts, (ii) do not test the study in an initial manner and (iii) create tension in the students. The draft policy proposes state census examinations in grades three, five and eight, to track and consider students' entire school experience. Further, the board recommends rescheduling the exams only to test key concepts, skills, and higher ordering abilities that will be important, as these board exams will be on a variety of subjects. Students will be able to choose their subjects and semesters when they want to appear for these board exams. School final exams can be replaced by board exams or its format can be changed.

7. School Infrastructure : The Committee noted that the establishment of primary schools in every settlement across the country has helped in increasing the availability and expansion of education. However, this has led to the development of very small schools (due to low student numbers). The small size of schools complicates the availability, selection, and efficiency of teachers and critical physical resources. Therefore, the draft policy recommends that several public schools be brought together to create school complexes. The complex will include a secondary school (grades nine to twelve) and all the public schools in its vicinity which provide education from pre-primary to eighth.

8. School complexes will include Anganwadadas, vocational education facilities and adult education centers. Each school complex will be a semi-autonomous unit that can provide integrated education to all at all stages from childhood to secondary education. This will ensure that resources such as infrastructure and properly trained teachers can be efficiently shared and expanded across the school complex.

9. Teacher Management : The Committee has noted that there has been a major increase in the shortage of teachers, shortage of professionally qualified and qualified teachers and

recruitment of teachers for non-academic reasons. The draft policy recommends that teachers be assigned to a specific school complex for at least five to seven years. Further, teachers will not be allowed to participate in any extracurricular activities during school hours (such as cooking lunch or participating in vaccination campaigns) that may affect their teaching ability.

10. Existing B.Ed. Courses and programs will be replaced by a four-year integrated B.Ed. This includes a program that combines high-quality materials, pedagogy and practical training. Integrated continuous professional development for all disciplines will also be created. It states that teachers will be required to complete at least 50 hours of continuous professional development training each year.

11. School Regulation: The draft policy recommends separating school regulation from aspects such as policy making, school running and educational development. It is proposed to set up an independent state school regulatory authority for each state, which will determine the basic uniform standards for public and private schools, determine the policy of the state education department and monitor and supervise the role of the state education department.

A Brief Review of School Education in the National Education Policy (NPE 2019) - a Childhood education - This policy emphasizes the seriousness of early year students and aims to ensure quality childhood care and education for all children between the ages of 3 and 6 by 2025.

b) Basic Literacy and Number of Students - Special attention will be given to elementary language and mathematics in class 1 to 5. The policy aims to ensure that every student in Class 5 and above achieves basic literacy and numbers by 2025, which is important.

c) Curriculum and pedagogy - A new developmental-appropriate curriculum and pedagogical structure for school education based on the principles of brain development and learning has been developed based on 5 + 3 + 3 + 4 design / design. The policy also stipulates that equal emphasis will be given to all subjects like science, social sciences, arts, languages and sports, mathematics, including the integration of professional and academic streams in schools.

d) Universal Admission- The policy aims to achieve 100% overall enrollment ratio for all school education by 2030 through various measures.

e) Equitable and Inclusive Education- The policy has a number of major and concrete initiatives to ensure that no child misses or misses out on any opportunity to learn and excel due to birth conditions or background. Special Education Zones will also be set up.

f) Teacher-Teacher recruitment will be done through a strong, transparent decision making process, promotions will be based on merit, multi-source periodical performance will be evaluated and there will be progress and ways to become an educational administrator or teacher.

g) School Administration - Schools will be organized in school complexes (clusters of 10-20 public schools) - will be the basic unit of governance and administration that will ensure availability of all resources - infrastructure, education (e.g. libraries) and people (e.g. arts). And music teacher) - with a strong professional teacher community.

h) Regulation of schools- Regulation and operation of schools will be done by independent bodies to eliminate conflicts of interest. There will be a clear, independent system for policy making, regulation, operations and education.

Summary -

The National Education Policy 2020 is the first education policy of the 21st century that aims to meet the growing development needs of our country. The policy proposes appropriate changes and improvements in all aspects of the national educational structure, including its regulation and administration, to build a new system that is consistent and effective with the ambitious goals of 21st century education, while building on the country's fundamental traditions and values. . The draft National Education Policy 2020 provided clarification regarding school education. In school education, early childhood education, basic literacy and numeracy, curriculum and pedagogy, universal access, equitable and inclusive education, teachers, school administration, regulation of schools, regulation of schools and formulation of policies to address conflicts of interest. It was mentioned that there would be a clear, separate system for operations and educational matters. Appropriate changes and various aspects have been highlighted by looking at the future educational thinking.

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